

Manual of the work: recent significant subseasonal fluctuations of supraglacial lakes on Greenland monitored by passive optical satellites

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1 Overview

This manual outlines the data processing workflow employed in the Greenland Supraglacial Lake (SGL) mapping project, which incorporates Python and JavaScript codes. The entire process is divided into six main steps: exporting remote sensing imagery from the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform, image preprocessing, SGL prediction using deep learning, image postprocessing, uncertainty assessment of SGL area estimates, and data visualization.

2 Input and settings

2.1 Exporting and filtering images

Based on the generated SGL occurrence grid shapefile, images are acquired for $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ grid cells at a temporal resolution of 5 days, applying additional filtering conditions to obtain cloud-free imagery. These remote sensing images are then exported from GEE to local storage, which requires sufficient disk capacity (preferably 10 TB or more).

The JavaScript script used for acquiring optical remote sensing images (both Landsat 8/9 and Sentinel-2) is named *Step1_Batch_export_images.js*, located in the folder `...\SGL_codes_with_manual\Code\Step1`. You will also need to import the “GrIS_Grid_10km_Periphery” table, whose shapefile is already included in `...\SGL_codes_with_manual\Example_data\Step1\SGL_occurrence_grid\`.

Figure 1: 10-km SGL occurrence grid partition over GrIS used as spatial constraints for satellite imagery archiving. Using historical Landsat mosaic imagery obtained from Chen et al. (2020) with manual visual discrimination, a total of 3,792 grids (blue-orange color) were retained from 21,799 grids (gray color) generated by ArcGIS. Grey lines outline six drainage basins, namely North (NO), North-East (NE), South-East (SE), South-West (SW), Center-West (CW), and North-West (NW), which are simply modified from Rignot and Mouginot (2012).

2.2 Image pre-processing

The Python script used for image pre-processing, which subdivides the $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ scenes into 256-pixel patches, is named *Step2_Batch_image_subset.py* and is located in `...\SGL_codes_with_manual\Code\Step2`. The input data consists of the large-scale $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ images, and the output consists of patches cropped according to the image acquisition date. Please ensure that the input and output paths are correctly specified, following the comments in the code.

2.3 Image prediction

The Python scripts for training the convolutional neural networks (CNN) model and predicting SGLs are located in ...*SGL_codes_with_manual*\Code*Step3*. A variety of classic CNNs were compared, and we ultimately adopted the AttSEResUNet architecture for extracting SGLs from NIR images. Using the enhanced NDWI ice mask and manual visual editing, we generated a batch of high-quality training datasets in both NIR and RGB categories. These datasets, along with the corresponding labels (limited to 6,567 images per category due to file size constraints), can be found in ...*SGL_codes_with_manual*\Train_test_dataset\.

Please note that the deep learning framework is built using TensorFlow's Keras implementation, so environment configuration may be required.

2.4 Derive SGL area time series

The SGL area time series is derived grid-by-grid from the SGL prediction patches during post-processing. The Python script for this step, named *Step4_PostProcess_SGL.py*, takes as input the subdivided remote sensing images, their corresponding prediction patches, and other auxiliary data (e.g., slope raster from ArcticDEM, GIMP ice sheet mask, and the generated SGL occurrence grid shapefile).

Please be aware that this script depends on the ArcPy Python package. Ensure that all file directories are properly organized according to the comments in the code.

2.5 Estimate the SGL area uncertainty

In this study, SGL area uncertainty is estimated by multiplying the outer contour perimeter by half the image pixel size, following equation (1). This straightforward yet effective approach has been used in previous studies on glacial lake area uncertainty estimation in High Mountain Asia (Salerno et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2023). Certain morphological operations (e.g., majority filtering and boundary cleaning) were applied when deriving the SGL perimeter to minimize the impact of fine-grained artifacts on contour extraction.

$$\partial A_i = P_i \times \frac{G}{2} \quad (1)$$

where ∂A_i is the uncertainty of SGL area, P_i is the corresponding perimeter, and G is the spatial resolution of satellite images (10 m pixel size here).

The Python script for estimating SGL area uncertainty is named *Step5_Uncertainty_assessment.py*. Again, ensure that all file directories are properly structured according to the comments in the code.

Figure 2: Time series of gridded SGL area changes during the ablation seasons from 2017 to 2022, taking grid #2747 as an example. The light shades represent SGL area error uncertainty.

2.6 Plot the SGL area time series

The Python script for plotting the main time series data from the paper is named *Step6_Plot_multi_time_series.py*. Spatial distribution plotting is done using Generic Mapping Tools (GMT), with the assistance of Mr. Jun Ding from the Gravity and Cryosphere Lab at SUSTech, to whom I extend my gratitude.

Follow the instructions in the code comments to correctly link each input file.

References

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